

Ethnomedical Uses of Fabaceae Plant Species for Primary Health Care by Rural Communities in Limpopo Province, South Africa

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The local biodiversity of indigenous flora is an important source of medicinal plants for traditional healthcare systems and is recognised by pharmaceutical industries for novel drug development. This review presents the medicinal uses of indigenous plant species in the family Fabaceae for primary healthcare needs among members of rural communities in the Capricorn District of Limpopo Province, South Africa. The review adopted a narrative literature review approach to describe the ethnomedical uses of these plant species, with a particular focus on evidence from South Africa and comparable contexts. The findings highlight the species' medicinal uses as both curative and preventive. The review shows similar uses of the medicines by other cultural groups, which suggests clinical investigations to test the claimed medicinal properties of the plant parts used and wider propagation of the species. This type of healthcare contributes to the United Nations' goal of achieving good health and well-being for all people.

Keywords: Traditional medicine, medical ethnobotany, Fabaceae, primary healthcare, Limpopo Province

Primary healthcare research involving indigenous medicinal plants has piqued the interest of social science and biomedical experts alike. These plants are used to treat a range of ailments, and there is a hypothesis that they may yield effective new therapeutic molecules with few or no adverse effects (Alum, 2024). Many underdeveloped countries still rely on medicinal plants for primary healthcare, a long-standing tradition (Chinyama, 2009). According to Nergawe et al. (2023), traditional medicine plays a substantial role in healthcare delivery, and there remains a strong reliance on plants as a source of medicine. According to Abena and Ekila (2018), traditional African medicine relies heavily on medicinal plants, with thousands of species used for their therapeutic properties. Rankoana (2022) concedes that this reliance is shaped by community beliefs in indigenous healthcare practices and the perceived efficacy of traditional remedies.

These plants contain therapeutically valuable metabolites and are therefore used as cost-effective remedies for human ailments (Anand et al., 2022). The global use of plant compounds for therapeutic purposes has increased significantly (Shah & Bhat, 2019). The pharmaceutical industry has utilised indigenous plants and their traditional medicinal practices, leveraging their antimicrobial properties and the potential to develop safe anticancer and antibacterial drugs (Babandi, 2025). This development supports Mongalo and Makhafola's (2018) claim that increased ethnopharmacological efforts have led to the isolation and identification of chemical compounds in numerous South African

medicinal plants.

The World Health Organization (WHO) recognises the value of medicinal plants from an ethnomedical perspective (Shah & Bhat, 2019). As demand for herbal medicine rises in both developed and developing countries, the WHO recommends improving the success rate of drug discovery by drawing on the indigenous knowledge of local communities (Gogoi et al., 2024). The biodiversity of indigenous flora is a significant source of medicinal plants for indigenous healthcare systems and is recognised by pharmaceutical industries for novel drug development (Alum, 2024; Naphade & Jadhav, 2025). Modern medicine has derived several notable drugs from the traditional knowledge of indigenous peoples (Shah & Bhat, 2019). Given modern medicine's reliance on compounds derived from natural products, there is a resurgence of interest in developing new pharmaceuticals from plants (Fekadu et al., 2024). Indigenous medicinal plants are a cornerstone of the pharmaceutical industry's discovery of novel medications, providing a rich source of bioactive compounds that can lead to effective treatments for various diseases (Soelberg et al., 2025).

This review summarises the medicinal uses of indigenous plant species in the family Fabaceae. It identifies a wide variety of species that people in rural areas of South Africa's Limpopo Province use as their primary source of healthcare. This review focuses on these therapeutic plants, drawing on published works in medical ethnobotany in the area. It stresses the need to document their cultural and medicinal importance and to preserve them. In addition, the review contributes to databases on medicinal plants, highlighting their capacity to produce novel bioactive substances that could provide new therapies and enhance knowledge of traditional medicine.

The review is prompted by observations that medicinal plants in the Fabaceae family are internationally recognised as important sources of medicine for primary health care (Alharbi & Al-Qthanin, 2020). Maroyi (2023) notes that bioactive chemical components such as phenolic acids, flavonoids, lectins, saponins, alkaloids, and

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carotenoids have been studied across several species in this family. Fabaceae species are effective in treating a wide range of illnesses in both animals and humans (Maroyi, 2023). With 751 genera and about 19,500 species, the Fabaceae are the second-largest family of medicinal plants in South Africa (Mhlongo & Van Wyk, 2019). Trees, shrubs, and herbaceous perennial and annual plants are the main components of these species, which are used as traditional medicines (Iwu, 2014; Semenya et al., 2013; Mhlongo & Van Wyk, 2019). These species contribute to the array of plants identified in other studies conducted in Limpopo Province, which could be used to develop new drugs that are readily accessible and cost-effective, particularly for addressing prevalent infections in the region.

Method

Previous research on the medical ethnobotany of four district municipalities in South Africa's Limpopo Province was analysed. A literature analysis was conducted to describe the ethnomedical uses of indigenous plant species in the family Fabaceae. The objective was to describe the species' ethnomedicinal importance and to investigate commonalities in their utilisation. The investigation was conducted in electronic databases, including Elsevier, Wiley Journals, Emerald Management Journals, and ScienceDirect. The main search criteria were publications on medicinal ethnobotanical knowledge and the medicinal uses of Fabaceae species. Emphasis was placed on the therapeutic use of plant species belonging to the Fabaceae family. Eligibility of the literature sources was based on empirical research and reviews on the uses of medicinal plants. The research of relevant literature was restricted to English-language publications.

Results and Discussion

Ten indigenous medicinal plants from the Fabaceae family have been identified in the literature on the ethnobotanical practices of

rural communities in the Capricorn District of Limpopo Province. Among these species, six are utilised for curative medical purposes, while five serve as preventive measures for primary healthcare. The data suggest that plant species in the family Fabaceae play a vital role in addressing various human infections. This family is among the most frequently employed in traditional health practices across South Africa. The family Fabaceae is abundant in species that are ecologically and culturally significant, particularly in arid regions of the planet (Molares & Ladi, 2011). The family encompasses numerous medicinal plants that are well-regarded for their applications in ethnomedicine and as food sources (Judd et al., 2002) and is characterised by distinctive morphological features, including its fruits and leaves (Rahman & Parvin, 2014). Fabaceae ranks among the botanical families richest in therapeutic properties within the pharmacopoeia of indigenous communities, owing to the diverse range of medicinal plants used for various health conditions and cultural practices (Molares & Ladi, 2011).

Mongalo and Makhafola (2018) acknowledge that the indigenous plant species predominantly used in the medical ethnobotany of rural communities in Limpopo Province belong to the Fabaceae family. This family is among the most preferred, as evidenced by numerous ethnobotanical surveys conducted in Limpopo Province (Mahwasane et al., 2013; Mongalo & Makhafola, 2018; Semenya & Maroyi, 2019). Additionally, Fabaceae have been recognised as one of the most utilised families in a range of ethnobotanical studies (e.g., Molares & Ladi, 2011; Semenya & Maroyi, 2019; Maroyi, 2021; 2023). This finding aligns with a study by van Wyk (2020) which identified Fabaceae as the most dominant plant family in sub-Saharan Africa. Furthermore, the largest number of exotic plants used by traditional healers in herbal preparations is from the family Fabaceae (Van Wyk & Gericke, 2000). The medicinal properties of Fabaceae species have also been documented in other regions globally, as shown in the research by Aumeeruddy and

Table 1

Health Benefits of Fabaceae

Botanical Name	Habit	Local name	Part used	Medicinal uses	Similarity in Medicinal Uses
<i>Caesalpinia decapetala</i> (Roth) Alston.	Tree	Mokgabane	Root	Decoction treats sexually transmitted diseases	None
<i>Cassia abbreviata</i> Oliv.	Shrub	Monepenepene	Root	Decoction treats sexually transmitted infections, and mellitus diabetes.	Magwede (2026)
<i>Elephantorrhiza elephantina</i> Burkhei Benth	Herb	Mošitšana	Root Leaf	Decoction treats blood purification. Leaf infusion treats stomach-ache and constipation	Maroyi (2017; 2021)
<i>Elephantorrhiza burkei</i> Benth.	Shrub	Mošitši-o Mogolo	Root	Decoction taken orally for STDs	Mathibela et al. (2018)
<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (L.) Wight and Arn. Fabaceae,	Shrub	Moretšhe	Root	Decoction treats infertility. Diabetes Leaves are used to treat Vomiting.	Semenya & Maroyi (2018); Mazimba et al. (2022)
<i>Faidherbia albida</i> (Delile) A. Chev	Tree	Mokgaba	Branch	Magically prepared branches treat infertility	None
<i>Kirkia acuminata</i> Oliv	Tree	Modumela	Bark	Sap squeezed to accelerate healing.	Maroyi (2017)
<i>Peltophorum africanum</i> Sond.	Shrub Tree	Mosehla Mphata	Bark Root	Infusion treats stomachache, ritual defilement. Decoction treats STDs	Mongalo (2016) Mathibela et al. (2019)
<i>Schotia brachypetala</i> Sond.	Tree	Molope	Bark Leaf	Decoction treats diarrhoea Leaf infusion used as an immune booster and cough	None
<i>Senna italica</i> Mill. Subsp. <i>Arachoides</i> (Burch) Lork	Tree	Morotela tshosi	Root	Infusion treats defilement	Mathibela et al. (2019)

Mahomoodally (2020) and Lawal et al. (2020). The research conducted by Tesfahuneygn and Gebreegziabhe (2019) and Frimpong et al. (2024) underscores the importance of Fabaceae species in traditional healing practices, highlighting their specific uses and cultural significance across diverse traditional medical systems. Semanya and Maroyi (2019) attribute the prevalence of Fabaceae species to their resilience in different environmental conditions.

Growth Form

Eleven medicinal plant species belonging to the family Fabaceae were identified in the literature on the ethnobotany of Limpopo Province. The predominant category is trees (55%), followed by shrubs (36%) and herbs (9%), as shown in Figure 1. This indicates that within Fabaceae species, trees and shrubs are the predominant growth forms. Mongalo and Raletjena (2023) reported the predominance of trees, shrubs, and herbs within Fabaceae plant species. These findings align with Maroyi's (2023) study on Fabaceae species used in traditional Zimbabwean medicine, in which trees and shrubs are recognised as principal sources of traditional remedies.

Figure 1

Growth Form of Fabaceae Species

Parts Used

Figure 2 shows that the most used parts for preparing medicines are the roots (45.4%), bark (27.2%), leaves (18.3%), and branches (9%). Mathabe et al. (2006) found that roots and bark were the most common components in herbal remedies made from Fabaceae species. Similarly, Papo et al. (2022) found that the roots, bark, and leaves are the most commonly used components of Fabaceae species. The same observations are reported by Maroyi (2023) that main parts used of medicinal Fabaceae species in Zimbabwe are their roots, leaves, and bark. Mateos-Aparicio et al. (2008) acknowledge that a single Fabaceae species can exhibit beneficial health effects, with distinct plant parts used for different therapeutic purposes, thereby supporting the medicinal potential of several plant parts from two species. There are two instances where medicinal uses of more than one plant material from the same plant have been reported. For example, the bark and roots of *Elephantorrhiza elephantina* (Burkhei) Benth are utilised for medicinal purposes, with the root decoction employed for blood purification and the leaf infusion used to treat stomach aches and constipation (Papo et al., 2022). Similarly, the bark and leaves of *Schotia brachypetala* Sond. serve medicinal roles, with the bark decoction used to treat diarrhoea and the leaf infusion acting as an immune booster and cleanser.

Figure 2

Plant Parts of Fabaceae Species

Preparation and Administration

Table 1 provides evidence regarding the routes of administration for medicines derived from Fabaceae plant species. Typically, the medicine prepared from the roots and bark of these species is administered orally in the form of a decoction, which involves boiling the plant parts (Van Wyk, 2020; Papo et al., 2022). Similarly, the leaves are infused in water to create a medicinal preparation that is also taken orally to address various ailments (Mongalo & Raletjena, 2026). Another method of administration involves the utilisation of raw materials; for example, a tree branch may be prepared for a specific purpose through traditional practices, or sap can be extracted from the bark to produce medicine (Rankoana, 2022). These methods of preparation and administration are corroborated by the findings of Frimpong et al. (2024) which indicate that medicines from Fabaceae species are predominantly prepared as decoctions and infusions for oral administration. Additionally, the studies conducted in India (Das et al., 2023) and Saudi Arabia (Amal & Masarrat, 2016) further support the notion that decoctions and infusions are the most prevalent methods of preparing medicinal plants from Fabaceae species.

Ethnomedical Uses of Fabaceae

Eight plant species from the Fabaceae family have been identified as sources of medicine used to address primary health care needs. They treat six main types of disease: those affecting the blood, the digestive system, the respiratory system, the reproductive system, defilement, and sexually transmitted infections (see Table 1). These species have therapeutic and preventive uses. Curative treatment for blood disorders, diabetes, and respiratory tract infections is primarily achieved using decoctions and infusions from eight species. In contrast, medical applications from two species are administered for prevention against diseases and defilement, such as employing extracts to enhance the immune system or to avert infections. Exploring the ethnomedical uses of these Fabaceae species in relation to other groups that have acknowledged their therapeutic virtues can enrich understanding of their history and practice. Further clinical investigation into the alleged therapeutic qualities of the plant components used and the promotion of the wider proliferation of species with proven utility in treating a variety of diseases and disorders are warranted in light of the correlations shown here.

Out of the ten species shown in Table 1, the following species showed significant commonalities in their therapeutic applications across different communities:

- *Cassia abbreviata* Oliv: Diabetes

- *Dichrostachys cinerea* (L.) Wight and Arn.: Diabetes
- *Elephantorrhiza burkei* Benth. STDs
- *Elephantorrhiza elephantina* Burkhei Benth: Used for stomach disorders.
- *Kirkia acuminata* Oliv: accelerates healing
- *Peltophorum africanum* Sond.: digestive systems disorders

Conclusion

Drawing on the ethnobotanical literature on the medical ethnobotany of rural communities in Limpopo Province, South Africa, this review presents information on indigenous medicinal plants in the family Fabaceae. Comprehensive healthcare benefits from the therapeutic uses of these species are primary care for both disease prevention and treatment. When it comes to improving patient outcomes and access to healthcare, this aligns with primary healthcare services across biomedical health systems. The review findings highlight the importance of integrating Indigenous healthcare practices with biomedical approaches to achieve the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 3, which aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all people at all ages. Similarities with other groups' ethnomedical practices are evident, even though the study does not include data on the safety or scientific validation of the therapeutic claims associated with the reported medicinal plants. This widespread use of the species calls for more clinical studies to verify the purported medicinal benefits of the plant components and to encourage their wider conservation for the potential benefit in treating a wide range of diseases and conditions. In addition to improving current biomedical treatments, this kind of study may pave the way for the creation of novel pharmaceuticals that could help communities afford comprehensive primary health care.

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